

Measurement Technique to Assess the Impact of RF Power Amplifier Memory Effects on Radar Performance

Carlos G. Tua, Student Member, IEEE
Radar Technology Branch
NSWC Dahlgren Division
Dahlgren, VA, USA

Abstract—Future Digital Array Radars (DARs) will have the capability to create arbitrarily shaped beams on receive, and flexible beam shaping on transmit. Their multifunction design supports a diverse set of waveforms, which when exercised can induce transient amplitude and phase shift in their solid state High Power Amplifiers (HPAs). This transient is due to electro-thermal effects and has duration in the order of 100's of microseconds to milliseconds, and is identified in this paper as a potential problem for future DARs. The time varying amplitude and phase can potentially impact the effectiveness of Pulse Doppler and Moving Target Indicator (MTI) processing in addition to changing antenna pattern characteristics over the duration of a Coherent Processing Interval (CPI). The purpose of this paper is to present a technique to measure electro-thermal memory effects as applied to multifunction DARs.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the future, Digital Array Radar (DAR) systems will migrate to element level digital beamforming (DBF) to enhance their performance. This allows for the creation of arbitrarily shaped beams, simultaneous beams on receive, and flexible beam shaping and nulling on transmit. They will also be multifunction in design, supporting a diverse set of waveforms, and offer the potential for increased dynamic range as compared to more conventional systems due to the use of distributed receiver exciter architecture [1], allowing for higher clutter cancellation ratios, improving Moving Target Indicator (MTI) and Pulse Doppler processing.

Many processes taking place in a DAR depend on two basic premises: a) that the amplitude and phase relationship of each antenna element is known, and b) that these relationships are constant over time. This is necessary to form antenna beams, and achieve and maintain calibration.

Laboratory testing of solid state High Power Amplifiers (HPAs) shows that under multifunction conditions, the pulse to pulse constant amplitude and phase assumption is not valid. Amplitude and phase shift of one half dB and several degrees respectively are seen to occur over time scales of several milliseconds on pulse trains where the duty cycle or pulse width varies between adjacent Coherent Processing Intervals

(CPIs). Electro-thermal effects [2] are the suspected cause of the amplitude and phase shift later discussed in this paper.

A problem emergent from the multifunction capabilities of DARs is identified. The time varying amplitude and phase can potentially impact two aspects of radar performance. The effectiveness of stationary clutter rejection in Pulse Doppler and Moving Target Indicator processing can be limited. Additionally, antenna pattern characteristics could change over time due to differences in the behavior of individual amplifiers.

A literature review [2-9, 12-14] on electro-thermal models had not revealed any existing predistortion models that can be directly applied to multifunction radar waveforms. There is a need to understand this problem more thoroughly and assess how it will impact radar performance as it applies to multifunction DARs with element level DBF.

This paper reports on the development of a measurement technique designed to aid in the investigation of the impact of electro-thermal memory effect in multifunction DARs. The paper also presents measurement results of four Gallium Nitride (GaN) HPAs when excited with multifunction radar waveforms.

II. ELECTRO-THERMAL MODELS REVIEWED

Solid state HPAs used in radars are routinely driven 1 to 4 dB into compression, to maximize output power and increase efficiency, limiting the number of behavioral models that can be used. The classical Volterra-series for instance can only be used to characterize weakly nonlinear systems [3]. Furthermore thermal analysis of high power GaN amplifiers, show that thermal resistance significantly changes depending on operating conditions [4].

There has been a significant amount of work done in developing behavioral models for amplifiers [1-9, 12, 13]. These models are used in many scenarios, from circuit design aids to the development of predistortion techniques, and are most often tailored to communication systems, with little mention of applicability to pulse radar waveforms.

A commonly used approximation to the heat transfer problem is a second order differential equation. From this, an expression is developed [5] to calculate dynamic junction temperature. This expression is used to construct an electro-thermal model for power amplifiers. The model was used to design a predistortion function to compensate for effects due to temperature changes in the junction.

Another behavioral model approach tailored towards communication systems using a Volterra-based modeling is the one presented in [6]. One interesting concept from this paper was the proposal of a model with two widely separated time-constants. This approach is intuitively logical as many amplifiers are composed of stages, each with their own properties that can be affected by temperature. The time constants discussed are on the order of 1 to 10 microseconds; however the time constant that is being observed in the experiment is in the order of 100's of microseconds to milliseconds.

The thermal feedback mechanism of amplifiers has been studied [7] where envelop transient analysis is used to predict the impact of the thermal effects in pulsed RF modes. The model is for the design of single pulse amplifiers for radar applications, and does not deal with multiple pulses.

The memory effects for thermal and bias circuits, using a two tone test [8] have been studied. The test uses an intermodulation distortion signal applied together with a two-tone signal to the input of the amplifier, the amplitude and phase of the test signal is adjusted until the third order intermodulation (IM3) products at the output of the amplifier are cancelled. The technique provides information to help in the design of amplifiers and associated predistortion circuits.

Memory effects have been shown to be closely linked to the biasing network [9] and self-heating on amplifiers. In general temperature fluctuation is considered a slow process; however, thermal resistance within a GaN semiconductor die can change quite rapidly with duty cycle selection [4] directly affecting the device gain, which in turn will affect the insertion phase due to AM-PM conversions.

Deviating from the stimulus used to develop the model can render the model useless, so special attention needs to be taken in the adaptation of behavioral model. For a comprehensive overview of power amplifier behavioral models see [2].

III. DEVELOPMENT OF A TEST SETUP AND PROCEDURE

A test setup and procedure was developed, to allow for the simultaneous characterization of two HPAs, under representative multifunction radar conditions. The parameters measured are analogous to the scattering parameters (S_{21}), in that both the input signal to the Device Under Test (DUT) and its output are downconverted and digitized, allowing measurement of complex amplitude and phase, see Fig. 1.

There are two aspects believed to be unique about this test setup, the Scheduler and the Waveform of Interest (WOI):

Scheduler: The Scheduler interleaves groups of pulses configured to form coherent processing intervals, mimicking notional multifunction radar conditions. A wide variety of waveforms can be added to the scheduler, each with its own

modulation, bandwidth, pulse width, duty cycle and number of pulses.

Waveform of Interest (WOI): The Waveform of Interest defines the specific CPI in a set of multiple CPIs being implemented by the Scheduler whose data is captured for subsequent analysis. What is unique about this is that the WOI will be instantiated N times, where N is the number of pulses in the CPI, instead of being repeated. This allows for the predistortion of each pulse independently.

Figure 1. Block diagram of test setup illustrating the sampling of the input signal to the Device Under Test (DUT) and its output.

The test setup was designed to behave similarly to a two channel DAR, carrying out pulse compression and Doppler processing in non-real-time after data collection. A total of two exciters and four receivers were implemented using instrumentation. The different sections of the test setup are described below:

A. Waveform synthesis:

All waveforms in the scheduler are instantiated in the control and analysis software. Each waveform, including the individual pulses from the WOI, is treated as an object, and all relevant waveform properties are contained within it.

The test setup allows for the analysis of each individual pulse within the WOI, which combined will also show how the amplifiers affects the waveforms across an entire CPI.

The flexibility of the design is such that the setup can reproduce multifunction radar waveforms with widely different parameters. For simplicity only two representative waveforms, whose parameters are listed in Table I, are used to present measured results in this paper.

TABLE I. WAVEFORM SPECIFICATION

Waveform Specifications		
Parameter:	Waveform of Interest	Preceding Waveform
Modulation:	Up Chirp Linear Frequency Modulation	
Bandwidth:	10 MHz	50 MHz
Pulse Width:	10 microseconds	50 microseconds
Duty Cycle:	10 %	1 %
Number of Pulses:	64	4
Pulse Repetition Frequency:	10 kHz	200 Hz
Dwell Time:	6.4 milliseconds	20 milliseconds

B. Exciter:

An Arbitrary Waveform Generator (AWG) serves as the exciter. The AWG is loaded with several waveforms, each following a particular order and repetition as specified by the scheduler. Two analog channels are used to drive the upconverter stages with two digital outputs used for receiver trigger and amplifier enable.

The enable signal is an important aspect of power amplifiers that cannot be overlooked, as this is the way solid state power amplifiers are used in pulsed radar system. The amplifier is turned off while the radar listens for the returns. This significantly helps in the overall power efficiency of the radar system, which in turn reduces the system cooling requirements, but it also contributes to the thermal cycling of the amplifier.

C. Up/Down Converter Design:

A two stage up converter was designed to support instantaneous bandwidths of up to 100 MHz, and is tunable across 500 MHz at S-band. It translates the exciter's signal from an intermediate frequency to S-band. The down converter stage uses the same frequency planning used on the upconverter, translating the sampled signal from S-band down to an IF that can be sampled by the receiver.

D. Receiver:

A Digital Storage Oscilloscope (DSO) is used as the digital receiver. It samples each of the four channels at 250 MSps.

E. Pulse Generator:

A digital delay & pulse generator is used as the synchronizer, providing triggers to the DSO to start the data collection.

F. Digital Down Conversion:

Due to the sampling frequency used; the IF signal aliases to 62.5 MHz center frequency. This signal is digitally down converted to baseband (inphase and quadrature) and is then decimated by a factor of two before storage in the waveform object.

G. Signal Processing:

As previously mentioned, the test setup performs signal processing similarly to a DAR, in the way it generates and collects data. The major signal processing function used in the analysis of the data is pulse compression, which is applied to each channel individually.

The pulse compression is performed by doing a cross correlation between the reference and the amplified signal. The reference signal is derived from the signal sampled at the input to the amplifier under test. The amplitude and phase of the peak of the pulse compression response is recorded and time tagged to a position in the CPI.

H. Calibration:

For any given data collection, the test setup is calibrated using a continuous WOI train, see Fig. 2; to thermally stabilize the device. The pulse amplitude and phase across the CPI is then measured and used to define the zero amplitude and phase baseline.

Figure 2. Sequence for calibration waveform, as used in the test setup; calibration waveform is the WOI repeated until thermal equilibrium is reached.

IV. MEASURED RESULTS

Four commercially available solid state HPAs, from Aethercomm, Model Number SSPA 2.9-3.5-100, were tested. Each is capable of producing high power (100 W) outputs, under multifunction radar conditions. The amplifiers were first excited with the WOI repeated continuously in a calibration mode until they reach thermal equilibrium, a period of typically 60 seconds. The amplifiers were mounted on a cold plate set at 25°C.

Data is captured on a CPI after the thermal equilibrium is reached. After pulse compression, the amplitude and phase of each pulse in the CPI was mapped to its corresponding position within the CPI as shown in Fig. 3. Each point in the graph is the resulting cross correlation peak for each processed pulse, separated into amplitude and phase. This set of measurements represents the accuracy of the test set up, with a standard deviation in amplitude and phase errors computed to 0.004dB and 0.03 deg. respectively. Although not shown the post pulse compression noise floor signal to noise ratio is approximately 70dB.

Figure 3. System accuracy for (a) amplitude and (b) phase; each pulse is mapped to its corresponding position within the CPI, data point represent the phase or amplitude of a single pulse.

After the calibration sequence, the scheduler is updated so that the WOI is preceded by a completely different waveform containing a different pulse width and duty cycle, simulating a multifunction radar. The new sequence is represented in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. Multifunction sequence, as used on the test setup.

Following the same process as before, the pulse amplitude and phase was traced to its corresponding position within the CPI as shown in Fig. 5. Notice the significant amplitude Fig. 5(a) and phase Fig. 5(b) shift that occurs over time on a pulse to pulse basis across the CPI. Amplitude shifts of around 0.12dB and phase shifts in excess of 5 degrees were observed with time constants calculated in the milliseconds. These results are repeatable; subsequence processed CPI's following the sequence shown on Fig. 4 yielded identical results. Four amplifiers were tested, and their performance while transitioning waveforms is shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 5. (a) Amplitude and (b) phase shift imposed by the amplifier when transitioning between multifunction CPIs.

Figure 6. Test results for four amplifiers; (a) amplitude and (b) phase shift.

V. FIRST ORDER MODEL

Following the electrical analogy for heat flow [10], the belief that the measured effects are related to heat and the observation that they follow an exponentially decaying function, one can make a first order approximation of the amplitude and phase curves in fig. 5 by solving a simple equation (Eq. 1).

$$V(t) = I \left(1 - \exp\left(\frac{-t}{\tau}\right) \right) + V_0 \quad (1)$$

Where V_0 is analogous to a voltage source and the initial state, τ is the time constant and I is the step current. Since Eq. 1 is nothing more than an exponentially decaying function, it can be adapted to describe the amplitude and phase shift observed. Where V_0 is the initial (amplitude or phase) state, τ is the time constant and I is the (amplitude or phase) step. Performing a three parameter fit to the data from Fig. 5(a) for amplitude and Fig. 5(b) for phase yields the results in table 2.

TABLE II. PARAMETERS TO DESCRIBE AMPLITUDE AND PHASE SHIFT ACROSS CPI

List of parameters		
Parameter:	Linear Amplitude	Phase (deg.)
Input Step (I)	-0.0071 A	5.00 A
Initial state (V_0)	1.0076 V	-6.77V
Time constant (τ)	3.62 milliseconds	1.69 milliseconds

The resulting approximated amplitude and phase shift is shown in Fig. 7(a) and 7(b) respectively. Notice that there is a small discrepancy at the beginning of the CPI, where the measured amplitude shift does not follow the model predictions. Although this suggests the approximation is insufficient to mathematically describe the problem, the model predictions for phase shift over time show excellent agreement with the data and are very encouraging. It should also be noted that the different amplifiers tested, while all following the exponential model, all have different time constants and initial conditions. This suggests the possibility that manufacturing differences in the thermal stack-up of each amplifier affecting heat transfer can result in slightly different behavior across a large number of devices.

Figure 7. Approximation of the (a) amplitude and (b) phase shift using a simple exponential decay equation.

VI. IMPACT OF AMPLITUDE AND PHASE SHIFT ON BEAMFORMING

Traditionally low sidelobes antenna patterns have been relegated to receive beams, usually in the form of amplitude weights such as Taylor. More recently, phase-only techniques [11] have been used to create lower sidelobes, nulls and sector nulls on transmit. Phase only nulling techniques are outside of the scope of this paper, therefore only an example using a uniform illuminated array will be presented.

It is important to maintain a known relationship between antenna elements, in order to form precise beams, and to predict and control the position of nulls in the antenna pattern. This is true for both transmit and receive. In radars the placement of nulls is essential to reduce clutter and to reduce interference from other sources. The null depth depends upon unknown errors in an RMS fashion. Realizing that the difference in amplitude and phase is what is important in a beam former, the results from Fig. 6 can be converted into amplitude and phase differences between elements, using HPA 1 as the reference. The resulting amplitude and phase difference over the CPI is shown in Fig. 8.

Analysis of the null depth in a 4 element array with uniform weighting indicates that such small errors limit the depth of the nulls, see Fig. 9. Although the null appears to be moving, this is an artifact due to the small number of elements; for a larger array the nulls will simply not be as deep. Something important to point out is that the null depth gets better as it progresses through the CPI, which is expected as the amplifier moves towards the calibrated state.

Figure 8. Relative (a) amplitude and (b) phase shift across CPI, in reference to HPA 1.

Figure 9. Null depth for a 4 element uniformly illuminated transmit array using measured errors.

VII. IMPACT OF AMPLITUDE AND PHASE SHIFT ON MTI AND DOPPLER PROCESSING

The non-linear phase shift observed in the test result can impact the Doppler processing and MTI clutter cancellation. The common physics of the amplifiers is at fault here, as the shape of the phase shift is very similar from amplifier to amplifier. Contrary to the nulls on transmit problem, these errors can be partially compensated by the DBF on received before MTI and Doppler processing, but only if they are known and ambiguous returns are ignored. The phase change is exacerbated if only a single amplifier is used, such as in the case of a passive phased array, as the averaging effect of having multiple amplifiers is not present.

Calculating the cancellation ratio between two sinusoids represented as phase vector (phasor) can provide insight into the effect that amplitude and phase shift has in MTI and pulse Doppler processing. Eq. 2 calculates the cancellation ratio between two phasors, with phase (V_p) and amplitude (V_A), found by evaluating Eq. 1 with the parameters from table 2. Fig. 10 shows the phasor cancellation ratio, as the CPI progresses the cancellation ratio improves significantly.

$$CR(n+1) = 10 \log_{10} \left[\left(\frac{2}{|z(n)|e^{i\phi(n)} - |z(n+1)|e^{i\phi(n+1)}} \right)^2 \right] \quad (2)$$

Where:

$$\begin{aligned} |z(n)| &= V_A \left(\frac{n}{PRF} \right) \\ \phi(n) &= V_P \left(\frac{n}{PRF} \right) \frac{\pi}{180} \end{aligned} \quad n=0,1,2,3,\dots \quad (3)$$

Figure 10. Cancellation ratio for two phasors with errors as calculated in section V.

VIII. FUTURE WORK

It is too premature to provide a quantitative analysis of the effects observed due to the limited number of amplifiers tested. Future work will expand on the number of amplifiers tested as well as evaluate different Class AB amplifiers pallets; expand the analysis of how this memory effect can impact radar performance; and look into ways to adapt existing behavioral models to the particular problem at hand in order to develop a predistortion technique that will correct for these memory effects.

IX. SUMMARY

A potential problem associated with multifunction DARS was identified. The behavior of individual amplifiers changes due to electro-thermal effects. Furthermore, manufacturing variability in each amplifier can result in slightly different behavior across a large number of devices. The time varying amplitude and phase shift can potentially impact the effectiveness of Pulse Doppler and MTI processing in addition to changing antenna pattern characteristics over time.

A test setup was constructed and later used to characterize four GaN HPAs under multifunction conditions. The measured results were presented along with a description of how these amplitude and phase shifts can affect radar performance. This investigation will continue with a systematic analysis of the causes and effects and will explore possible solutions to the problem.

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